

Rank Polymorphism at Work

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Abstract

This pearl demonstrates how rank-polymorphism enables programmers to abstract performance-tuning aspects into the ranks and shapes of function arguments. Using prefix sum as an example, we show how a single, generic rank-polymorphic specification can represent an entire class of traditionally separate algorithmic specifications that differ in performance characteristics but not in the overall outcome.

The genuine elegance of this approach lies in the observation that, once encoded within a dependently-typed language, we can prove that certain classes of argument reshaping do not affect the overall computational outcome. Consequently, this establishes the equivalence of all corresponding algorithmic specifications, which in classic (typically imperative) settings would be extremely tedious, if feasible at all.

1 Introduction

Rank polymorphism is a language feature that permits the definition of functions operating on arrays of arbitrary rank. As an illustration, consider a function that adds two numeric arrays element-wise; the same definition applies to 0-dimensional, 1-dimensional, . . . arrays. A common justification for supporting rank polymorphism is its facilitation of generic programming: rather than providing a separate definition for each array rank, a single definition suffices for all ranks. This reduces the likelihood of errors, curtails verbosity, and—because compositions of rank-polymorphic operations yield more general specifications—encourages programmers to contemplate corner cases that might otherwise be overlooked [13]. Arguably, this is a principal reason why specifications in the APL [12] family are exceptionally terse.

Although this interpretation of rank polymorphism dates back to the 1960s, the present pearl offers a fresh perspective on the core idea, showing that, when rank polymorphism is made to work harder, it yields considerably richer benefits.

First, rank polymorphism gives rise to the notion of algorithmic equivalence. For a given rank-polymorphic function one can often define an equivalence relation on array shapes such that reshaping an array within the same equivalence class does not affect the computed values. A simple example is the sum of all array elements—the resulting value remains unchanged regardless of the shape assigned to the input array (provided that reshapes neither add nor remove elements).

Second, if array shapes are endowed with a richer structure than a mere sequence of dimensions, rank polymorphism becomes a tool for performance engineering. As Okasaki demonstrated [21], the choice of data structures determines algorithmic complexity in functional languages. Analogously, we show that the choice of array shape influences the

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complexity of array-based algorithms. Consider a rank-polymorphic function together with a shape equivalence relation such that all inputs in the same class produce identical results. Assuming a fixed evaluation strategy and runtime costs, reshapes within the equivalence class dictate the actual execution time while preserving the computed values. Consequently, one can identify an optimal shape that minimises runtime cost. Our analysis readily accommodates arbitrary assumptions about the underlying hardware—including parallelism, memory hierarchy, cache sizes, and so forth.

The principal technical contribution of this work is a precise formulation of the above ideas via a framework in Agda, which enables us to define: (i) rank-polymorphic arrays (Section 2); (ii) equivalence classes of shapes (Section 4); and (iii) runtime-cost models (Section 6).

Using the scan algorithm as a running example, we (i) encode a rank-polymorphic version of scan; (ii) prove that all scans belonging to a chosen shape-equivalence class compute identical results; (iii) devise a cost model for an idealised multicore processor; and (iv) demonstrate the runtime impact of reshaping.

When we introduce rank-polymorphic arrays, we deliberately avoid fixing the representation of arrays to any particular data structure. We achieve this by specifying an array theory that stipulates assumptions about shapes and indices, whilst requiring the concrete array datatype to be a representable functor. Our running example and accompanying equivalence proof are presented without committing to a specific model, meaning that they can be instantiated for any admissible representation. Thus, we may (a) define array representations and basic combinators in Agda; (b) perform performance engineering to select optimal array shapes for a given representation; and (c) subsequently instantiate our algorithm for that representation, preserving the established correctness guarantees. In the remainder of the paper we guide the reader through the rationale behind our design choices and the technical details of each component of the framework. This paper is an Agda script available at [25].

2 Arrays

In array programming the structure of array shapes is of central importance. The richer the shape structure, the more expressive the array combinators that can be derived. Conversely, poorly chosen shape encodings may inhibit expressivity and reasoning. To motivate this, we consider definitions of top-down and bottom-up recursive array traversals, which frequently arise in divide-and-conquer algorithms.

We work in a dependently-typed setting and require array types to guarantee index safety. A natural way to achieve this is to index an array type by its shape. Shapes are usually represented as a sequence of natural numbers, each specifying the bound of the index along a particular dimension. The crucial question, however, is which data structure should be used to represent shapes so that the definitions of our recursive traversals are not obscured by encoding artefacts.

At first sight, `List` appears to be a sensible choice. Consider the following abstract array type:

$$\text{Ar} : \text{List } \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{Set} \rightarrow \text{Set}$$

where the first argument denotes the shape and the second argument denotes the element type. We deliberately omit a concrete representation of the array itself.

With this definition, a top-down recursive array traversal can be expressed as follows:

103 $\text{top-down} : (\forall \{n\ s\} \rightarrow \text{Ar } ([n] ++ s) X \rightarrow \text{Ar } s X) \rightarrow (\text{Ar } [] X \rightarrow X) \rightarrow \forall s \rightarrow \text{Ar } s X \rightarrow X$
 104 $\text{top-down } f z [] \quad a = z a$
 105 $\text{top-down } f z (x :: s) a = \text{top-down } f z s (f a)$
 106

107 if we know how to reduce n s -shaped arrays into a single s -shaped array (the first argument
 108 f) and we know how to extract the element from an array of the empty shape¹ (the second
 109 argument z), then we can reduce arrays of any shape into X by repeatedly applying² f
 110 followed by a single application of z .

111 The bottom-up case, where we wish to reduce an s -shaped array of n -element arrays to an
 112 s -shaped array, is considerably less straightforward:
 113

114 $\text{bottom-up} : (\forall \{n\ s\} \rightarrow \text{Ar } (s ++ [n]) X \rightarrow \text{Ar } s X) \rightarrow (\text{Ar } [] X \rightarrow X) \rightarrow \forall s \rightarrow \text{Ar } s X \rightarrow X$
 115

116 The difficulty stems from the fact that **Lists** are built by pre-pending elements on the left.
 117 Consequently, pattern matching on a list proceeds left-to-right, whereas a bottom-up traversal
 118 naturally requires right-to-left unfolding. This problem is well known [29]; one solution
 119 proposed in the literature [16] introduces a view type:
 120

121 $\text{data View} : \text{List } \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{Set where} \quad \{-\# \text{TERMINATING } \#\}$
 122 $[] : \text{View } [] \quad \text{bottom-up } f z s a \text{ with view } s$
 123 $_{::}'_ : (s : \text{List } \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow (n : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{View } (s ++ [n]) \quad \dots | [] \quad = z a$
 124 $\text{view} : (xs : \text{List } \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \text{View } xs \quad \dots | s ::' n = \text{bottom-up } f z s (f a)$
 125

126 We use **view** to turn the list into the view type, and then we pattern-match on it. Agda does
 127 not recognise that **bottom-up** is terminating, hence we use explicit annotation. We can fix this
 128 by defining a measure on the length of the shape that decreases on every recursive call.
 129

130 Here we can see that representing shapes as **Lists** is suboptimal. Firstly, view types together
 131 with the termination argument would clutter any reasoning about bottom-up traversals,
 132 potentially rendering them more complex than the approach presented above. Secondly, the
 133 shape itself *does not* convey information about the traversal direction; consequently we must
 134 write two separate definitions, as the direction is dictated by the code rather than by the
 135 data. Finally, our arrays are *not* representation-independent, because we are committed to
 136 encoding shapes as **Lists**. Representation independence is crucial, since the interplay between
 137 hardware architecture and algorithm determines the preferred array storage. For example,
 138 many numerical problems involve arrays in which large portions of the elements are zero,
 139 giving rise to compressed storage schemes that omit the zeros and traverse only the non-zero
 140 entries. On systems with hierarchical memory, it is important to tile arrays into blocks that
 141 are stored contiguously in memory. Hence, we aim to formulate array types and algorithms
 142 orthogonal to the data layout, allowing the layout to be chosen later according to the specific
 143 requirements.
 144

145

146

2.1 Array Theory

147

148 In this section we propose an alternative approach that avoids the shortcomings identified
 149 above.

150

¹Usually arrays of the empty shape are singletons, meaning that they contain exactly one element.

151

²In the second equation of **top-down**, the argument a has shape $(x :: s)$, but f expects the shape $[n] ++ s$. However, the latter normalises to $(n :: s)$, therefore f can be applied to a .

152

153

We resolve the issue of traversal direction by encoding shapes as binary trees. In this formulation the shape alone determines whether a traversal proceeds top-down or bottom-up.

A right-nested tree such as $(a, (b, (c, d)))$ —the right diagram—induces a top-down traversal, whereas a left-nested tree such as $((a, b), c), d$ —the left diagram—yields a bottom-up traversal. Moreover, this representation can express shapes that cannot be captured by simple lists, for example $((a, b), (c, d))$.

We achieve representation independence of arrays and shapes by defining a minimalist *array theory*. In this case we fix an interface to shapes, indices and arrays; we define some constraints, but the actual implementation of these structures will be given by concrete models. We define our array theory as follows:

```

record Array : Set1 where
  field
    S      : Set                ℓ↔      : P (ℓ n) ↔ Fin n
    P      : S → Set           ⊗↔      : ∀ {s p} → P (s ⊗ p) ↔ (P s × P p)
    ℓ      : ℕ → S             Ar      : S → Set → Set
    _⊗_    : S → S → S       Ar↔    : ∀ {s} → (P s → X) ↔ Ar s X

```

The theory draws inspiration from container theory [1], introducing restrictions on the kind of shapes that are allowed, and generalising the notion of container interpretation. As our positions are finite, the work on combinatorial species is likewise pertinent in this context [35].

The theory consists of shapes \mathbf{S} and positions (indices) \mathbf{P} within such shapes. We require two constructors for \mathbf{S} : ℓ which lifts a given natural number into \mathbf{S} and $_ \otimes _$ which builds a shape out of a left and a right sub-shapes.

Positions \mathbf{P} of a given shape s characterise all the valid indices into arrays of that shape. We require two properties of \mathbf{P} . Firstly, $\ell \leftrightarrow$ requires indices of a singleton shape ℓn to be isomorphic (denoted by \leftrightarrow) to the natural numbers $[0 \dots n]$ which is denoted by the type $\mathbf{Fin} n$. Secondly, $\otimes \leftrightarrow$ requires indices of a product shape to be isomorphic to the product of left and right sub-indices.

For readers familiar with universes, our theory says that (\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{P}) is a monoidal³ universe where $(\ell 1)$ is a unit.

\mathbf{Ar} is a type of arrays and $\mathbf{Ar} \leftrightarrow$ requires \mathbf{Ar} of shape s to be isomorphic to a function from indices of shape s to array elements. Note a distinction with the container theory, where the interpretation of the container (S, P) for some X is fixed to $\Sigma (s : S) (P s \rightarrow X)$. Here we only

³A universe (U, EI) where there exists ϵ and $*$, such that $(U, \epsilon, *)$ is a monoid, and EI is a monoid homomorphism into $(\mathbf{Set}, \top, _ \times _)$.

say that that \mathbf{Ar} has to be a representable functor [9] (e.g. $(\mathbf{Ar} s)$ is isomorphic to $(\mathbf{P} s \rightarrow X)$). The concrete storage layout is left to the model.

2.2 Array operations

For any array model A , we can expand the isomorphisms of the array theory into operations on shapes, indices, and arrays. We group these operations into a module that we call \mathbf{ArOps} which is parametrised by A :

```

213 module ArOps (A : Array) where
214   imap : (P s → X) → Ar s X      ϕ : Fin n → P (ι n)      fst  : P (l ⊗ r) → P l
215   _[]_ : Ar s X → (P s → X)     ψ : P (ι n) → Fin n      snd  : P (l ⊗ r) → P r
216                                     _⊗_ : P l → P r → P (l ⊗ r)

```

The forward direction of the $\mathbf{Ar} \leftrightarrow$ isomorphism gives us a function that we call \mathbf{imap} (sometimes called *tabulate*); the backward direction gives us selections into arrays for which we use a C-like notation $_[]_$. Similarly, when expanding $\iota \leftrightarrow$ and $\otimes \leftrightarrow$ we obtain convenient operations on indices: ϕ and ψ which translate between the one-dimensional indices and $\mathbf{Fin} n$; \mathbf{fst} and \mathbf{snd} project left and right sub-indices from the index of a product shape; and $_⊗_$ makes an index of a product shape from two sub-indices of the corresponding sub-shapes.

2.2.1 Equality of Arrays

Using the selections from the previous section, we can define the notion of point-wise equality of two arrays $_ \approx_a _$ and show that \approx_a is an equivalence relation, meaning that \mathbf{Ar} with \approx_a is a setoid.

```

231   _ ≈a _ : Ar s X → Ar s X → Set      refl-≈a : a ≈a a
232   a ≈a b = ∀ ix → a [ ix ] ≡ b [ ix ]  sym-≈a : a ≈a b → b ≈a a
233   trans-≈a : a ≈a b → b ≈a c → a ≈a c

```

2.3 Models

The array theory of Section 2.1 imposes only the essential constraints needed for the subsequent reasoning, thereby accommodating a broad spectrum of models. To illustrate this flexibility we sketch several alternatives (omitting the equivalence proofs). Firstly, we can represent shapes as lists of natural numbers, and we can represent arrays as free monads of Agda's \mathbf{Vec} type:

```

242   data Tensor (X : Set) : List ℕ → Set where
243     pure : X → Tensor X []
244     roll  : Vec (Tensor X s) n → Tensor X (n :: s)

```

Putting this together we have a model:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{List} \mathbb{N}; \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{All} \mathbf{Fin}; \iota = _[]_; _⊗_ = _++_; \mathbf{Ar} s X = \mathbf{Tensor} X s.$$

As another example, let us consider a flat vector model:

$$\mathbf{S} = \mathbb{N}; \mathbf{P} = \mathbf{Fin}; \iota = \mathbf{id}; _⊗_ = _*__; \mathbf{Ar} n X = \mathbf{Fin} n \rightarrow X.$$

Shapes are natural numbers (tree structure is not preserved), positions are offsets given by \mathbf{Fin} , the shape product is a multiplication of natural numbers, and arrays are stored as functions.

A more traditional representation of vectors can be achieved by choosing a model where arrays are stored as cons lists:

$$S = \mathbb{N}; P = \text{Fin}; \iota = \text{id}; _ \otimes _ = _ * _; \text{Ar } n \ X = \text{Vec } X \ n$$

We can also encode less obvious choices as a model of the array theory: in high-performance computing it is often beneficial to use compressed formats, where arrays do not store zeroes. In this case, for a decidable X , one can encode arrays as a triple $((X, \text{Linked } n \ (P \ s), \text{Vec } n \ X))$, where the first element is the default element that is not stored (zero), the second element is a strictly increasing list of indices, and the third element is a list of values corresponding to each index in the second list.

The multitude of possible models suggests that it would be advantageous to identify a universal model in which we can develop our proofs and subsequently translate them to all other models. Such a construction is presented in the following subsection.

2.3.1 Initial Model

Let us define a smallest model that satisfies all the equations of the theory. Following terminology from model theory, we call such a model *initial*. This model has the property that any expression written in it can be lifted into any other model of the same theory. Moreover, this lifting is unique up to isomorphism. We define the initial model for our array theory and we demonstrate its initiality by defining lifting operations.

Shapes are defined as binary trees where ι constructs leaves and $_ \otimes _$ combines two sub-trees into a new one. Positions are predicates over shapes also given by two constructors: ι and $_ \otimes _$. A position for the shape $\iota \ n$ can be constructed by providing an index of type $\text{Fin } n$. Positions of product shapes can be constructed if positions of the left- and right-sub-shapes can be constructed. Arrays of shapes s with elements of type X are functions from $P \ s$ into X .

module I where

```

data S : Set where
   $\iota$  :  $\mathbb{N} \rightarrow S$ 
   $\_ \otimes \_$  :  $S \rightarrow S \rightarrow S$ 
data P : S  $\rightarrow$  Set where
   $\iota$  :  $\text{Fin } n \rightarrow P \ (\iota \ n)$ 
   $\_ \otimes \_$  :  $P \ s \rightarrow P \ p \rightarrow P \ (s \otimes p)$ 
Ar : S  $\rightarrow$  Set  $\rightarrow$  Set
Ar s X = P s  $\rightarrow$  X

```

Now we use the data types and constructors introduced above to define the model that we call A . We omit the definition for $\iota \leftrightarrow$, $\otimes \leftrightarrow$, $\text{Ar} \leftrightarrow$ as they hold trivially.

```

A : Array
A .Array.S = S
A .Array.P = P
A .Array. $\iota$  =  $\iota$ 
A .Array. $\_ \otimes \_$  =  $\_ \otimes \_$ 
A .Array.Ar = Ar

```

Note that we place these definitions in the module named I , obtaining a namespace that we will use to refer to initial shapes, positions, *etc.* in other contexts.

2.3.2 Initiality

We show that expressions defined within the initial model can be lifted into any other model that we denote A . As before, we put all the lifting operations into the module called FromInit that is parametrised by A .

Firstly, we define the operation $\llbracket _ \rrbracket s$ which lifts initial shapes (of type $I.S$) into the shapes defined in A (of type S).

module FromInit (A : Array) where

307 $\llbracket _ \rrbracket s : \mathbf{I.S} \rightarrow \mathbf{S}$
 308 $\llbracket \mathbf{I.l} \ n \rrbracket s = \iota \ n$
 309 $\llbracket s \ \mathbf{I.l} \otimes \ p \rrbracket s = \llbracket s \rrbracket s \otimes \llbracket p \rrbracket s$

310 Note, that in general we cannot translate \mathbf{S} shapes into $\mathbf{I.S}$ shapes because \mathbf{S} may contain
 311 shapes that are not representable in $\mathbf{I.S}$. Also, for most of the models, $\llbracket _ \rrbracket s$ is not going to be
 312 injective, e.g. take \mathbf{S} to be \mathbb{N} and \otimes to be $*$.

313 Next, $\llbracket _ \rrbracket p$ translates initial positions (of type $\mathbf{I.P}$ s) into positions in the model A (of type
 314 \mathbf{P}) of lifted shapes ($\llbracket s \rrbracket s$). As translated positions are of a lifted shape, we can define an
 315 inverse of $\llbracket _ \rrbracket p$ that we call $\llbracket _ \rrbracket p'$.

316 $\llbracket _ \rrbracket p : \forall \{s\} \rightarrow \mathbf{I.P} \ s \rightarrow \mathbf{P} \ \llbracket s \rrbracket s$ $\llbracket _ \rrbracket p' : \forall \{s\} \rightarrow \mathbf{P} \ \llbracket s \rrbracket s \rightarrow \mathbf{I.P} \ s$
 317 $\llbracket \mathbf{I.l} \ i \rrbracket p = \phi \ i$ $\llbracket _ \rrbracket p' \ \{\mathbf{I.l} \ n\} \ i = \mathbf{I.l} \ (\psi \ i)$
 318 $\llbracket i \ \mathbf{I.l} \ \otimes \ j \rrbracket p = \llbracket i \rrbracket p \otimes \llbracket j \rrbracket p$ $\llbracket _ \rrbracket p' \ \{s \ \mathbf{I.l} \ \otimes \ p\} \ i = \llbracket \mathbf{fst} \ i \rrbracket p' \ \mathbf{I.l} \ \otimes \ \llbracket \mathbf{snd} \ i \rrbracket p'$

319 Finally, $\llbracket _ \rrbracket a$ lifts initial arrays of initial shapes into arrays of lifted shapes. Similarly to
 320 position lifting, $\llbracket _ \rrbracket a$ has an inverse $\llbracket _ \rrbracket a'$ from the arrays of *lifted* shapes.

321 $\llbracket _ \rrbracket a : \forall \{s\} \rightarrow \mathbf{I.Ar} \ s \ X \rightarrow \mathbf{Ar} \ \llbracket s \rrbracket s \ X$ $\llbracket _ \rrbracket a' : \forall \{s\} \rightarrow \mathbf{Ar} \ \llbracket s \rrbracket s \ X \rightarrow \mathbf{I.Ar} \ s \ X$
 322 $\llbracket a \rrbracket a = \mathbf{imap} \ \lambda \ i \rightarrow a \ \llbracket i \rrbracket p'$ $\llbracket _ \rrbracket a' \ a \ i = a \ \llbracket i \rrbracket p$

323 We show that array and position lifting are inverses by proving the following four equalities⁴:

324 $\llbracket \llbracket i \rrbracket p \rrbracket p' \equiv i$ $\llbracket \llbracket i \rrbracket p' \rrbracket p \equiv i$ $\llbracket \llbracket a \rrbracket a \rrbracket a' \ \mathbf{I.l} \ \approx_a \ a$ $\llbracket \llbracket a \rrbracket a' \rrbracket a \approx_a \ a$

3 Defining Scan

325 We use generalised prefix sums (typically referred to as *scan*) as a running example that helps
 326 us demonstrate the proposed technique. Mathematically, prefix sums on vectors of numbers
 327 can be specified as

$$s_i = \sum_{j < i} a_j$$

328 For a given input vector a , we compute a vector s (of the same length as a) whose i -th element
 329 is the sum of the i -th prefix of a , i.e. all the elements of a up to index i . If the element a_i is
 330 included in the sum, such a prefix sum is called *inclusive*; otherwise it is called *exclusive*. In
 331 the remainder of the paper we concentrate exclusively on the exclusive version.

332 This specification can be generalised to vectors containing elements of an arbitrary type X ,
 333 provided with a binary operation on X that replaces addition and a neutral element of type X
 334 that replaces zero. Such a generalisation is called *scan*.

3.1 Scan on Vectors

335 We begin with the definition of *scan* on one-dimensional arrays, which are often called
 336 vectors. We introduce the `Vec` type as a shorthand for one-dimensional arrays in the initial
 337 model. The first argument of `Vec` is the length of the vector and the second argument is the
 338 type of the vector elements. We also define the standard operations on vectors that will be
 339 used in the scan: `nil`⁵ constructs the empty vector; `cons` constructs a vector of length $1 + n$
 340

341 ⁴Agda struggles to infer hidden variables s in some cases, so in the actual code we have to supply them explicitly,
 342 but we omit them here for readability.

343 ⁵The definition uses the absurd pattern (see <https://agda.readthedocs.io/en/v2.7.0.1/language/function-definitions.html#absurd-patterns> for more details), because Agda recognises that an index of type `Fin 0` could not possibly exist.

358 given an element and a vector of length n ; the two standard destructors, head and tail, are
 359 denoted by `hd` and `tl` respectively.

360 $\text{Vec} : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \text{Set} \rightarrow \text{Set}$ $\text{nil} : \text{Vec } 0 \ X$ $\text{hd} : \text{Vec } (\text{suc } n) \ X \rightarrow X$
 361 $\text{Vec } n \ X = \text{Ar } (\iota \ n) \ X$ $\text{nil } (\iota \ ())$ $\text{hd } v = v \ (\iota \ \text{zero})$
 362
 363 $\text{tl} : \text{Vec } (\text{suc } n) \ X \rightarrow \text{Vec } n \ X$ $\text{cons} : X \rightarrow \text{Vec } n \ X \rightarrow \text{Vec } (\text{suc } n) \ X$
 364 $\text{tl } v \ (\iota \ i) = v \ (\iota \ (\text{suc } i))$ $\text{cons } x \ v \ (\iota \ \text{zero}) = x$
 365
 366 $\text{cons } x \ v \ (\iota \ (\text{suc } i)) = v \ (\iota \ i)$

367 With these definitions at hand, `scan` on vectors can be defined as follows:

368 $\text{scan} : (X \rightarrow X \rightarrow X) \rightarrow X \rightarrow \text{Vec } n \ X \rightarrow X \times \text{Vec } n \ X$
 369 $\text{scan } \{n = 0\} \ f \ acc \ v = acc, \ \text{nil}$
 370 $\text{scan } \{n = \text{suc } _ \} \ f \ acc \ v = \text{let } s, \ v = \text{scan } f \ (f \ acc \ \$ \ \text{hd } v) \ (\text{tl } v)$
 371 $\text{in } s, \ \text{cons } acc \ v$
 372
 373

374 The function takes the binary operation f as its first argument, a running value acc (initially
 375 the neutral element of f) as its second argument and the n -element vector v as the third one.
 376 The function produces a tuple where the first projection is a reduction of f over v ; and the
 377 second projection is a vector where each i -th index contains the reduction of f over the prefix
 378 of v up to (but not including) the i -th element.

379 In the case when the length of v is zero ($n = 0$), the second projection is the empty vector.
 380 When the input length is a successor of some number, we call `scan` recursively on the tail of
 381 v , adding the head of v to the accumulator. We update this result by prepending the old value
 382 of the accumulator to the second projection of the returned pair.

383 Note that the primary purpose of the `scan` presented here is to provide a specification of a
 384 one-dimensional scan algorithm. This version will serve as a reference point in Sections 3.2
 385 and 5 when proving the correctness of other scan implementations. Consequently, representing
 386 vectors using initial arrays (implemented as functions) is appropriate: it simplifies later proofs,
 387 and we do not assume that this particular code will be executed at runtime.

388 Finally, observe that the binary operation f used in `scan` has arguments of the same type,
 389 which differs from the conventional definitions of scan found in the standard libraries of
 390 functional languages such as Agda or Haskell. Throughout the remainder of the paper we
 391 restrict ourselves to scans on associative operations, for which the arguments must indeed
 392 share a common type. Nevertheless, it is worth mentioning that the usual, more general form
 393 of scan can be recovered⁶ through scanning on function composition.
 394
 395

396 3.2 Array Combinators

397 We have seen the definition of `scan` on vectors (initial one-dimensional arrays), and now we
 398 wish to derive a rank-polymorphic version for all models.
 399

400
 401 ⁶A general version of scan uses a binary operation of type $X \rightarrow Y \rightarrow Y$. We recover this version by scanning with a
 402 (non-dependent) function composition as the binary operation. We compute a composition of partial applications of
 403 f for each index, and then apply the resulting functions to the neutral element:

404 $\text{scan}' : (X \rightarrow Y \rightarrow Y) \rightarrow Y \rightarrow \text{Vec } n \ X \rightarrow Y \times \text{Vec } n \ Y$
 405 $\text{scan}' \ f \ e \ a = \text{let } s, \ a = \text{scan } _ \circ' \ _ \ \text{id } (f \circ' \ a) \ \text{in}$
 406 $s \ e, \ (\lambda i \rightarrow a \ i \ e)$
 407
 408

We express a rank-polymorphic version of `scan` using a suite of primitive array combinators such as `map`, `zip`, *etc.* In principle, all of these combinators can be defined in the initial model and then lifted into the model of interest. However, doing so may introduce considerable inefficiency. As a practical illustration, consider an array representation that does not store zeroes. In that case, point-wise summation of two arrays needs only inspect the non-zero elements of both arrays. By contrast, a naïve point-wise summation would traverse the entire index space, thereby accessing every element of both argument arrays.

To retain representation independence, we abstract over concrete implementations of the combinators. We define a record called `Comb` that specifies the interfaces to array combinators; this record is parameterised by the array model A . This is analogous to defining a type class in Haskell, meaning that *different* implementations of the combinators can be chosen for each array model. The definition of `Comb` follows:

```
record Comb : Set1 where
  field
    K      : X → Ar s X
    map    : (X → Y) → Ar s X → Ar s Y
    nest   : Ar (s ⊗ p) X → Ar s (Ar p X)
    unnest : Ar s (Ar p X) → Ar (s ⊗ p) X
    unzip  : Ar s (X × Y) → Ar s X × Ar s Y
    zipWith : (X → Y → Z) → Ar s X → Ar s Y → Ar s Z
    scanv  : (X → X → X) → X → Ar (ι n) X → X × Ar (ι n) X
```

`K` returns a constant array whose elements are all equal to its argument; `map` applies a supplied function to every element of an array; `nest` and `unnest` convert between arrays of product shapes and nested arrays; `unzip` and `zipWith` behave like their list-based counterparts; `scanv` implements `scan` on rank-one arrays. Note that `Ar` of a fixed shape constitutes an applicative functor [17], which gives rise to `K`, `map`, `zipWith` and `unzip`. The `nest/unnest` combinators stem from the monoidal structure of shapes, and `scanv` is specific to our use-case.

At present the array combinators impose no behavioural constraints. Consequently, different models could choose implementations of the same combinator that yield divergent results, making it impossible to reason about the values produced by a generic (model-independent) array expression that employs these combinators. We resolve this issue by providing canonical implementations for the combinators in any model. These implementations are collected in the record `CanonComb`, defined as follows:⁷

```
CanonComb : Comb A
CanonComb .K x      = imap λ i → x
CanonComb .map f a  = imap (f ∘ a [ _ ])
CanonComb .nest a   = imap λ i → imap λ j → a [ i ⊗ j ]
CanonComb .unnest a = imap λ i → a [ fst i ] [ snd i ]
CanonComb .unzip f  = CanonComb .map proj1 f, CanonComb .map proj2 f
CanonComb .zipWith f a b = imap λ i → f(a [ i ]) (b [ i ])
```

⁷We use copatterns (see <https://agda.readthedocs.io/en/v2.7.0.1/language/copatterns.html>) to define the fields of the `CanonComb` record.

460 `CanonComb .scanv f e a = let s , a' = Vec.scan f e [a] a' in s , [a'] a`

461

462

463 Note that `scanv` is defined using the implementation given in Section 3.1, by lifting the
 464 implementation from the initial model. All canonical combinators compute a function from
 465 indices to values, which is then turned into an actual array by `imap`.

466 `CanonComb` supplies default implementations of the combinators for every model, yielding
 467 two benefits. First, any array expression that uses combinators can be instantiated in any
 468 model by employing these defaults. Second, and more importantly, `CanonComb` endows
 469 the combinator instances with a well-defined semantics. If a model provides more efficient
 470 implementations for certain combinators, these may be used provided they preserve the
 471 semantics. To formalise this requirement we introduce the record `CombOk`, which is
 472 parameterised by the array model A and by a concrete implementation of the combinators for
 473 A , denoted `Native`. We demand that every native combinator compute the same values (as
 474 defined by `_≈a_`) as the canonical implementation.

475

476 `record CombOk : Set1 where`

477 `field`

478 `K-ok : (x : X) → (Native.K x : Ar s X) ≈a Canon.K x`

479 `map-ok : (f : X → Y) (a : Ar s X) → Native.map f a ≈a Canon.map f a`

480 `nest-ok : (a : Ar (s ⊗ p) X) → Native.nest a ≈a Canon.nest a`

481 `unnest-ok : (a : Ar s (Ar p X)) → Native.unnest a ≈a Canon.unnest a`

482 `unzip-ok : (a : Ar s (X × Y))`

483 `→ Pointwise _≈a_ _≈a_ (Native.unzip a) (Canon.unzip a)`

484 `zipWith-ok : (f : X → Y → Z) (a : Ar s X) (b : Ar s Y)`

485 `→ Native.zipWith f a b ≈a Canon.zipWith f a b`

486 `scanv-ok : (f : X → X → X) (e : X) (a : Ar (t n) X)`

487 `→ Pointwise _≡_ _≈a_ (Native.scanv f e a) (Canon.scanv f e a)`

488

489 We prefix native combinators that originate from a parameter with `Native` and canonical
 490 combinators with `Canon`.⁸ The comparison of products in `unzip-ok` and `scanv-ok` uses
 491 `Pointwise`, which takes two relations (e.g. R_1 and R_2) and relates the first components of a
 492 pair via R_1 and the second components via R_2 .

493 Obviously, `CanonComb` satisfies `CombOk` trivially; this is witnessed by `CanonCombOk` of
 494 the following type (the definition is omitted for brevity):

495

496 `CanonCombOk : CombOk A (CanonComb A)`

497

498

499

3.3 Generalised Scan

500

501 We define `scan` for a given array model A , a collection of combinators N , and a proof that the
 502 combinators respect the intended semantics (witnessed by `Ok`) as follows:

503

504 `module Scan (A : Array) (N : Comb A) (Ok : CombOk A N) where`

505

506

507 ⁸`Canon` is merely a wrapper for `(CanonComb A)`.

508

509

510

```

511 scan : (s : I.S) → (X → X → X) → X → Ar [(s)]s X → X × Ar [(s)]s X
512 scan (I.ι x) f e a = scanv f e a
513 scan (s I.⊗ p) f e a = let
514     m , a = unzip (map (scan p f e) (nest a))
515     r , m' = scan s f e m
516     a' = zipWith (map ∘ f) m' a
517     in r , unnest a'

```

Note that `scan` is defined for arrays of the *lifted* shape s (of type `I.S`). This is necessary because `scan` is defined inductively on shapes: for singleton shapes we apply `scanv`; for product shapes we recurse into sub-arrays, scan the array of carries, and then update the sub-arrays with the scanned carries. This induction works only if we can decide whether a shape is a product or a singleton. In some models this decision is unavailable (*e.g.* when shapes are natural numbers), hence we employ lifted shapes.

We also provide two projections, `scan1` and `scan2`, for the carry and for the scanned array respectively:

```

529 scan1 s f e a = scan s f e a .proj1      scan2 s f e a = scan s f e a .proj2

```

3.4 Scan at Work

We illustrate the above implementation by applying it to a two-dimensional array of natural numbers, using addition as the binary operation and 0 as the neutral element (Fig. 1). Colours

Fig. 1. Application of rank-polymorphic `scan` to 2-dimensional array of natural numbers.

distinguish arrays from operations. The array a (green, top-left) of shape $(\iota 2 \otimes \iota 6)$ is the input. It is fed to a function (purple) that maps `scan` across the rows of a and `unzip`s the array of pairs into a pair of arrays. Solid arrows indicate inputs to functions; striped arrows indicate outputs. The pair (shown in a dotted box, top-right) consisting of partial sums (carries) and scanned rows. We denote the projections of this pair by m and a' respectively. Both m and a' are coloured yellow, signalling temporary data. Scanning the partial sums m produces a pair containing the overall sum r and a scan of the partial sums m' . The overall sum r is coloured red because it forms the first output of the whole scan. Finally, we adjust the rows of a' by adding the corresponding element from m' to each row, *i.e.* adding 0 to the first row and 21 to

562 the second row. We transform the nested array into an array of product shape using `unnest`.
 563 This adjusted array constitutes the second output of the scan and is likewise coloured red.

564

565

3.5 Initial Scan

566

567

568

As `scan` is defined for all models, it can be instantiated for the initial model with the canonical combinators:

569

```
module IS = open Scan I.A (CanonComb I.A) (CanonCombOk I.A)
```

570

571

572

573

This instance of `scan` is noteworthy because we can prove that, for any array model A and for any semantically-respecting combinators, the results computed by `scan` for that model coincide with those computed by the initial scan. Formally:

574

$$\text{scan-ok} : (s : \mathbf{I.S}) \rightarrow (f : X \rightarrow X \rightarrow X) \rightarrow (e : X) \rightarrow (a : \mathbf{Ar} \llbracket s \rrbracket s X)$$

575

$$\rightarrow \text{scan}_1 \text{ s f e a} \equiv \mathbf{IS}.\text{scan}_1 \text{ s f e} \llbracket a \rrbracket a'$$

576

577

$$\times \text{scan}_2 \text{ s f e a} \approx_a \llbracket \mathbf{IS}.\text{scan}_2 \text{ s f e} \llbracket a \rrbracket a' \rrbracket a$$

578

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589

The theorem follows from the parametricity $\llbracket \rrbracket$ of `scan` over array models and the initiality of the initial model. Unfortunately, there is no straightforward way to internalise this result as an Agda proof which is needed in the subsequent section. In principle one could define an embedded language, re-express the array theory and combinators within it, and then prove a general parametricity result à la $\llbracket \rrbracket$. However, such an approach would considerably complicate the exposition. Instead, we prove the theorem manually, demonstrating that the translation artefacts introduced by moving between models do not affect the computed values. In essence, the theorem states that all scans in all models compute the same values: whenever two models A and B share the same (lifted) shape and the same element values, their respective scans produce identical results.

590

4 Reshaping

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One common operation on arrays is an element-preserving change of shape that we call **reshape**. In principle, **reshape** can be regarded as an isomorphism between the index spaces of two corresponding arrays. However, in many situations we are interested only in a subset of all possible permutations. In particular, we frequently consider an equivalence relation on shapes such that reshapes within the same equivalence class preserve certain operations, for example `scan`.

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Reshape relations make it possible to achieve this by defining a “language” of shape transformations, each of which induces a permutation of array elements. The relation presented below captures those reshapes that preserve array flattening. The reshape relation plays a central role in the stability proof in Section 5.

For any array model A , **Reshape** is an inductive relation that relates shapes s and p when the products of these shapes (*i.e.* the numbers of elements in the flattened arrays) are identical.

605

```
data Reshape : S → S → Set where
```

606

```
  eq : Reshape s s
```

607

```
  _⊕_ : Reshape s p → Reshape q r → Reshape (s ⊗ q) (p ⊗ r)
```

608

```
  _·_ : Reshape q p → Reshape s q → Reshape s p
```

609

```
  split : Reshape (ι (m * n)) (ι m ⊗ ι n)
```

610

```
  flat : Reshape (ι m ⊗ ι n) (ι (m * n))
```

611

612

613 The relation is equipped with an identity constructor `eq`, composition `_·_`, gluing of two
 614 individual reshapes into a reshape of a product `_⊕_`, and, most importantly, `split` and `flat`
 615 which give rise to reversible array flattenings.

616 With the given definition of `Reshape` we can show that it is symmetric:

```
617 rev : Reshape s p → Reshape p s
618
619 rev eq      = eq
620 rev (r ⊕ r₁) = rev r ⊕ rev r₁
621 rev (r · r₁) = rev r₁ · rev r
622 rev split   = flat
623 rev flat    = split
624
```

625 Consequently, `Reshape` is an equivalence relation: it is reflexive by `eq`, symmetric by `rev`,
 626 and transitive by `_·_`. Hence `Reshape` forms a setoid, allowing us to employ the convenient
 627 reasoning syntax demonstrated in the `leftn` proof. A number of interesting shape relations
 628 can be derived from the properties of the natural numbers. As an illustration, consider the
 629 relation between a singleton shape and its product with a singleton `ι 1`. We use `flat` to turn
 630 `_⊗_` into multiplication on natural numbers and exploit the neutrality of multiplication to
 631 finalise the definition.

```
633 leftn : ∀ n → Reshape (ι 1 ⊗ ι n) (ι n)
634 leftn n = begin
635     ι 1 ⊗ ι n ≈⟨ flat ⟩
636     ι (1 * n) ≡⟨ cong ι (*-identity! _) ⟩
637     ι n
638
639     ■ where open ReshapeReasoning
640
```

641 `Reshape` has the following contra-variant action on indices:

```
642 _⟨_⟩ : P p → Reshape s p → P s
643 i ⟨ eq      ⟩ = i
644 i ⟨ r ⊕ r₁ ⟩ = (fst i ⟨ r ⟩) ⊗ (snd i ⟨ r₁ ⟩)
645 i ⟨ r · r₁ ⟩ = i ⟨ r ⟩ ⟨ r₁ ⟩
646 i ⟨ split   ⟩ = φ $ combine (ψ $ fst i) (ψ $ snd i)
647 i ⟨ flat    ⟩ = let a, b = remQuot _ (ψ i) in φ a ⊗ φ b
648
```

649 As can be observed, `eq` has no effect; `_⊕_` acts on the corresponding sub-indices; composition
 650 `_·_` applies two actions in sequence; and `split` and `flat` employ an isomorphism between `Fin(m`
 651 `* n)` and `Fin m × Fin n` given by `combine` and `remQuot`.

652 Finally, `reshape` on arrays is defined by means of selection on reshaped indices:

```
654 reshape : Reshape s p → Ar s X → Ar p X
655 reshape r a = imap λ ix → a [ ix ⟨ r ⟩ ]
656
```

657 We show that reshaping forwards followed by reshaping backwards yields the identity, via
 658 the following lemmas:

```
659 revrev      : (r : Reshape s p) (i : P p) → i ⟨ r ⟩ ⟨ rev r ⟩ ≡ i
660 revrev'     : (r : Reshape s p) (i : P s) → i ⟨ rev r ⟩ ⟨ r ⟩ ≡ i
661 rev-reshape-≈ : (r : Reshape s p) (a : Ar s X) → reshape (rev r) (reshape r a) ≈a a
662
663
```

Moreover, we prove that reshapes are congruent: if two arrays contain the same elements, then reshaping them with a given r produces arrays that also contain the same elements:

$$\text{reshape-cong} : \{a b : \text{Ar } s X\} (r : \text{Reshape } s p) \rightarrow a \approx_a b \rightarrow \text{reshape } r a \approx_a \text{reshape } r b$$

The proof proceeds by induction on r , establishing that `reshape` merely permutes the elements according to their indices; consequently, the results of reshaping two extensionally equal arrays are themselves extensionally equal.

Note that `Reshape` is a proof-relevant relation, which means that different expressions of the type `Reshape s p` may exhibit distinct actions on indices and arrays. In the present instance this situation does not arise, and `Reshape` captures arbitrary permutations of the elements in the shape tree. Consequently, there is no mechanism to transpose an array via `reshape`.

For example, consider the array $[[1, 2, 3], [4, 5, 6]]$ of shape $(\iota 2 \otimes \iota 3)$. There exists a `Reshape` $(\iota 2 \otimes \iota 3) (\iota 3 \otimes \iota 2)$; however, its action yields the array $[[1, 2], [3, 4], [5, 6]]$ rather than the desired transposition $[[1, 4], [2, 5], [3, 6]]$.

If we were to extend `Reshape` with a `swap` constructor, we could define a transpose operation. In that scenario we would have two reshapes of the same type that behave differently. We do not introduce `swap` here because doing so would preclude us from demonstrating the stability of the scan under reshapes.

In general, one should envisage many reshape relations—potentially organised hierarchically—that serve distinct purposes.

4.1 Initial Reshapes

As with shapes and indices, reshapes within the initial model can be translated into reshapes within any other model as follows:

$$\llbracket _ \rrbracket r : \text{IR.Reshape } s p \rightarrow \text{Reshape } \llbracket s \rrbracket s \llbracket p \rrbracket s$$

as with indices, translated reshapes act on lifted shapes.

Furthermore, we can show that lifting reshaped arrays is the same as reshaping lifted arrays with lifted reshapes:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{reshape-}\llbracket _ \rrbracket : (r : \text{IR.Reshape } s p) (a : \text{I.Ar } s X) &\rightarrow \llbracket \text{IR.reshape } r a \rrbracket a \approx_a \text{reshape } \llbracket r \rrbracket r \llbracket a \rrbracket a \\ \text{reshape-}\llbracket _ \rrbracket' : (r : \text{IR.Reshape } s p) (a : \text{Ar } \llbracket s \rrbracket s X) &\rightarrow \llbracket \text{reshape } \llbracket r \rrbracket r a \rrbracket' a \text{I} \approx_a \text{IR.reshape } r \llbracket a \rrbracket a' \end{aligned}$$

Again, while this is not surprising, this requires a formal proof which can be found in [25].

5 Reshape independence of Scan

In this section we demonstrate that `scan` is stable under reshapes; that is, any reshaping of the input array expressible with `Reshape` has no effect on the values computed by the `scan`.

We fix a monoid with binary operation $_ \langle + \rangle _$ and neutral element ϵ . We then prove that initial scans are stable under initial reshapes. Two theorems are employed: `init-scan1-ok` requires the carries to be equal, whereas `init-scan2-ok` requires the array elements to be equal:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{init-scan1-ok} : (a : \text{Ar } s X) (r : \text{Reshape } s p) & \\ \rightarrow \text{IS.scan}_1 p _ \langle + \rangle _ \epsilon (\text{reshape } r a) &\equiv \text{IS.scan}_1 s _ \langle + \rangle _ \epsilon a \\ \text{init-scan2-ok} : (a : \text{Ar } s X) (r : \text{Reshape } s p) & \\ \rightarrow \text{IS.scan}_2 p _ \langle + \rangle _ \epsilon (\text{reshape } r a) &\approx_a \text{reshape } r (\text{IS.scan}_2 s _ \langle + \rangle _ \epsilon a) \end{aligned}$$

Both proofs proceed by induction on the reshape r . For the `eq`, `_⊕_` and `_·_` constructors the argument follows straightforwardly from the inductive hypothesis. The `split` and `flat` constructors, however, require additional reasoning, because we must relate the application of the operation to sub-vectors with the operation applied to the whole vector. Subsequently, the proof concerning carries proceeds as follows. We invoke `scan-ok` to convert to an initial scan over lifted arrays; then we translate lifted reshapes into initial ones using `reshape-[]`; the stability of initial scans is applied to eliminate the reshaping, and finally we apply `scan-ok` in reverse:

```

715 scan-thm1 : ∀ s p → (a : Ar [ s ]s X) (r : IR.Reshape s p)
716           → scan1 p _⟨+⟩_ ∈ (reshape [ r ]r a) ≡ scan1 s _⟨+⟩_ ∈ a
717
718 scan-thm1 s p a r = begin
719   scan1 p _⟨+⟩_ ∈ (reshape [ r ]r a)   ≡⟨ scan-ok p _ _ .proj1 ⟩
720   IS.scan1 p _⟨+⟩_ ∈ [ reshape [ r ]r a ]a' ≡⟨ IS.scan1-cong _ _ _ (reshape-[] r a) ⟩
721   IS.scan1 p _⟨+⟩_ ∈ (IR.reshape r [ a ]a') ≡⟨ init-scan1-ok _ r ⟩
722   IS.scan1 s _⟨+⟩_ ∈ [ a ]a'           ≡⟨ scan-ok s _ _ .proj1 ⟩
723   scan1 s _⟨+⟩_ ∈ a
724   ■ where open ≡-Reasoning

```

The proof for arrays follows exactly the same structure as the preceding theorem, and is therefore omitted:

```

725 scan-thm2 : ∀ s p → (a : Ar [ s ]s X) (r : IR.Reshape s p)
726           → scan2 p _⟨+⟩_ ∈ (reshape [ r ]r a) ≈a reshape [ r ]r (scan2 s _⟨+⟩_ ∈ a)

```

Our rank-polymorphic specification of `scan` can be viewed as an infinite family of algorithms, one for each array shape. The `Reshape` equivalence partitions shapes into equivalence classes, and the foregoing proof establishes that `scan` applied to any two shapes within the same class yields identical results. In the “what/how” metaphor, the *what* remains unchanged whilst the *how* may be systematically varied through the application of `reshape`.

6 Runtime Effects

In this section we demonstrate how the runtime properties of `scan` can be controlled by reshaping the input array. To make observations we extend our specification by introducing effects that we expect to appear during actual execution. These effects do not interfere with the computations themselves, so all the previous results remain applicable.

Effects are introduced via an abstract traversable [17] monad M :

```

738 module Effectful (M : Set → Set) (isMon : Monad M)
739           (sync : ∀ {s X} → I.Ar s (M X) → M (I.Ar s X)) where

```

M is a module parameter, as is the function `sync` (the analogue of `sequenceA` in Haskell) which makes M traversable. Consequently, all functions in this module are parametric [22] in M and cannot exploit its internal structure. The only “interface” to M consists of `return`, `_»=_` and `sync`. By instantiating M as the identity monad, all effects disappear and we recover the original definition of `scan`. Although we do not prove this formally, it should be evident from the code. We work in the initial model, and as before we first define an effectful scan on vectors and then on arrays of arbitrary rank. The source of effects is the binary operation

766 (the first argument of `scan`), which now returns $M X$ instead of X , and the algorithm must
 767 propagate these effects; consequently the return type of `scan` is wrapped in M .

768 When scanning vectors we propagate effects left-to-right, sharing the computation of the
 769 i -th element with that of the $(i + 1)$ -st:

```
770 scanv : (X → X → M X) → X → Vec n X → M (X × Vec n X)
771 scanv {n = zero } f e v = return (e , nil)
772 scanv {n = suc n} f e v = do e' ← f e (hd v)
773                               s , v' ← scanv f e' (tl v)
774                               return (s , cons e v')
```

777 In the rank-polymorphic scan, one-dimensional arrays are handled by `scanv`. For arrays of
 778 product shapes we apply `scan` to all sub-arrays (conceptually in parallel), then gather the
 779 effects produced by these computations using `sync`. We bind the partial results to m and a' so
 780 that m and a' share the computation. Next we scan the array of carries m (obtaining r and
 781 m') and adjust the sub-arrays of a' with the elements of m' (again conceptually in parallel)
 782 before accumulating all the effects of this adjustment:

```
783 scan : (X → X → M X) → X → Ar s X → M (X × Ar s X)
784 scan {s = ι n} f e a = scanv f e a
785 scan {s = s ⊗ p} f e a = do m , a' ← unzip <$> (sync $ map (scan f e) (nest a))
786                               r , m' ← scan f e m
787                               a'' ← sync $ unnest $ zipWith (map ∘ f) m' a'
788                               return (r , a'')
```

791 Comparing this with the implementation from the previous section, we have replaced `lets`
 792 with `dos` and introduced accumulation of effects via `sync` in two places. It is easy to see that
 793 when M is the identity monad, the above definition collapses to the earlier one.
 794

795 6.1 Left and Right Nesting

797 To illustrate runtime differences when evaluating arrays of differing shapes, we define
 798 reshapes that convert arbitrary shape trees into left- and right-nested forms. Conceptually,
 799 this technique of right/left traversals applied to scans can be found in [7]; however, here we
 800 achieve the alteration of the algorithm by a single reshape, since we have an explicit handle
 801 on the array shape.
 802

803 First we define a reshape that flattens a shape tree into a singleton shape. We introduce a
 804 function that computes the product of the tree's elements, denoted `_b`, and the corresponding
 805 reshape, called `br`:

```
806 _b : S → N          br : Reshape s (ι (s b))
807 (ι n) b = n          br {ι x} = eq
808 (s ⊗ p) b = s b * p b  br {s ⊗ p} = flat ∙ (br ⊕ br)
```

810 Next we define a helper reshaping that reassociates shapes consisting of three sub-shapes.
 811 The definition flattens all three components, applies associativity of multiplication, and then
 812 unflattens the shapes:

```
813 assocr : Reshape ((s ⊗ p) ⊗ q) (s ⊗ (p ⊗ q))
814 assocr {s} {p} {q} =
```

816

```

817 begin
818   (s ⊗ p) ⊗ q ≈ ⟨ (br ⊕ br) ⊕ br ⟩
819   (ι (s b) ⊗ ι (p b)) ⊗ ι (q b) ≈ ⟨ flat • (flat ⊕ eq) ⟩
820   (ι ((s b * p b) * q b)) ≡ ⟨ cong ι (ℕ.*-assoc (s b) _) ⟩
821   (ι (s b * (p b * q b))) ≈ ⟨ (eq ⊕ split) • split ⟩
822   (ι (s b) ⊗ (ι (p b) ⊗ ι (q b))) ≈ ⟨ rev br ⊕ (rev br ⊕ rev br) ⟩
823   (s ⊗ (p ⊗ q))
824
825   ■ where open ReshapeReasoning
826

```

With these helpers we can define operations that nest shape trees to the right. The left-pointing triangle in the notation indicates the leaf direction. Analogous to flattening, we define the operation on shapes \triangleleft using the helper \triangleleft_* , which right-nests the first argument while leaving the second unchanged:

```

832   _△_* : S → S → S           _△_* : S → S
833   (ι n) △_* q = ι n ⊗ q       (ι n) △_* = ι n
834   (s ⊗ p) △_* q = s △_* (p △_* q)   (s ⊗ p) △_* = s △_* (p △_*)
835

```

We lift these functions to reshapes, obtaining $\otimes \Rightarrow \triangleleft_r$ and \triangleleft_r as follows:

```

837   ⊗ ⇒ △_*r : Reshape (s ⊗ p) (s △_* p)           △_*r : Reshape s (s △_*)
838   ⊗ ⇒ △_*r {ι n} = eq                               △_*r {ι n} = eq
839   ⊗ ⇒ △_*r {s ⊗ p} = ⊗ ⇒ △_*r • (eq ⊕ ⊗ ⇒ △_*r) • assocr   △_*r {s ⊗ p} = ⊗ ⇒ △_*r • (eq ⊕ △_*r)
840
841

```

For left-nested shape trees the code is symmetric:

```

843   _▷_* : S → S → S           _▷_* : S → S
844   s ▷ (ι x) = s ⊗ ι x       (ι x) ▷_* = ι x
845   s ▷ (p ⊗ q) = (s ▷ p) ▷ q   (s ⊗ p) ▷_* = (s ▷_*) ▷_* p
846
847
848   ⊗ ⇒ ▷_*r : Reshape (s ⊗ p) (s ▷ p)           ▷_*r : Reshape s (s ▷_*)
849   ⊗ ⇒ ▷_*r {s} {ι x} = eq                               ▷_*r {ι x} = eq
850   ⊗ ⇒ ▷_*r {s} {p ⊗ q} = ⊗ ⇒ ▷_*r • (⊗ ⇒ ▷_*r ⊕ eq)   ▷_*r {s ⊗ p} = ⊗ ⇒ ▷_*r • (▷_*r ⊕ eq)
851   • rev assocr
852
853

```

We leave it as an exercise for the reader to verify that the above code indeed computes the intended nestings; a proof can be found in the paper source [25]. An example application of both functions would be:

```

857 sample-shape : S
858 sample-shape = (ι 2 ⊗ ι 3) ⊗ ((ι 4 ⊗ ι 11) ⊗ (ι 5 ⊗ ι 6) ⊗ ι 7)
859
860 right-nested : sample-shape △_* ≡ ι 2 ⊗ (ι 3 ⊗ (ι 4 ⊗ (ι 11 ⊗ (ι 5 ⊗ (ι 6 ⊗ ι 7))))))
861 right-nested = refl
862
863 left-nested : sample-shape ▷_* ≡ (((((ι 2 ⊗ ι 3) ⊗ ι 4) ⊗ ι 11) ⊗ ι 5) ⊗ ι 6) ⊗ ι 7
864 left-nested = refl
865
866
867

```

6.2 Observation

Finally we construct a monad that enables reasoning about the complexity and parallelism of `scan`. The monad M combines a writer [34] and a reader. The writer component counts the number of binary operations performed during the scan, while the reader component records whether the evaluation proceeds sequentially or in parallel:

```

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$$\begin{array}{ll}
 M : \text{Set} \rightarrow \text{Set} & _ \gg = _ : M X \rightarrow (X \rightarrow M Y) \rightarrow M Y \\
 \text{data Par} : \text{Set where} & M X = \text{Par} \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \times X & (m \gg = f) p = \text{let } n, x = m p \\
 \text{goPar goSeq} : \text{Par} & \text{return} : X \rightarrow M X & m, y = f x p \\
 & \text{return } x p = 0, x & \text{in } m + n, y
 \end{array}$$

The `Par` datatype therefore distinguishes sequential (`goSeq`) from parallel (`goPar`) execution. The natural number paired with X in M “carries” the operation count. The `return` of M performs no binary operations, incurring zero cost in either mode; the bind operator `__>>=_` executes its argument in the chosen mode, then runs the resulting function in the same mode, summing the operation counts of both invocations: We define `sync` to model parallel execution on an idealised CPU with a fixed number of threads that run in parallel. Within each thread the code runs sequentially, and both start-up and synchronisation costs are assumed to be zero. Two helper operations, `vpar` and `vseq`, compute respectively the maximum and the sum of the first projections in a given vector. Conceptually, this reflects the idea that the time required to execute n items of work in parallel is dictated by the slowest item, whereas the time for sequential execution is simply the sum of the individual runtimes:

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$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \text{vpar} : \text{Vec } n (\mathbb{N} \times X) \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \times \text{Vec } n X & \text{vseq} : \text{Vec } n (\mathbb{N} \times X) \rightarrow \mathbb{N} \times \text{Vec } n X \\
 \text{vpar } v = \text{fold } \mathbb{N}._ \sqcup _ 0 (\text{proj}_1 \circ v) & \text{vseq } v = \text{fold } \mathbb{N}._ + _ 0 (\text{proj}_1 \circ v) \\
 , \text{proj}_2 \circ v & , \text{proj}_2 \circ v
 \end{array}$$

We assume our idealised CPU has eight threads. The scheduling algorithm for a vector of n work items proceeds as follows. When executing items in parallel we split them evenly among the threads and run each sub-vector sequentially; when executing sequentially we simply process each item in order and accumulate the total runtime. For arrays we first flatten them into vectors and then apply the same strategy:

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$$\begin{array}{ll}
 \text{vsync} : \text{Vec } n (M X) \rightarrow M (\text{Vec } n X) & \text{sync} : \text{Ar } s (M X) \rightarrow M (\text{Ar } s X) \\
 \text{vsync } \{n\} v \text{ goPar} & \text{sync } a p = \text{let} \\
 \text{rewrite } m \equiv m \% n + [m/n] * n \text{ } 8 \{ \{ \text{it} \} \} = \text{let} & n, t = \text{vsync } (\text{reshape } b_r a) p \\
 r, q = \text{vsplit } \{n \% 8\} v & \text{in } n, \text{reshape } (\text{rev } b_r) t \\
 \#r, r' = \text{vseq } (\lambda i \rightarrow r i \text{ goSeq}) & \\
 \#q, q' = \text{vpar } \lambda j \rightarrow \text{vseq } \lambda i \rightarrow & \\
 \quad \text{vnest } \{m = n / 8\} q i j \text{ goSeq} & \\
 \text{in } \#r + \#q, \text{vjoin } r' (\text{vunnest } \lambda i j \rightarrow q' j i) & \\
 \text{vsync } v \text{ goSeq} = \text{vseq } (\lambda i \rightarrow v i \text{ goSeq}) &
 \end{array}$$

In `vsync` we employ the theorem `m ≡ m % n + [m/n] * n` to rewrite the length n as $n \% 8 + (n/8) * 8$. The function `vsplit` then divides the vector into two parts of lengths $n \% 8$ (the remainder) and $(n/8) * 8$. Subsequently `vnest` reshapes the latter into a nested vector of size $n/8 \times 8$. We run the eight sub-vectors of length $n/8$ in parallel (each sub-vector is processed sequentially). The time taken for the remainder is added to the overall runtime, assuming the slowest thread

919 handles it. Finally we reassemble the results using `vjoin` and `vunnest`, which are inverses of
 920 `vsplit` and `vnest`.

921 We run `scan` on an array a of natural numbers with shape $(\iota\ 10 \otimes \iota\ 10 \otimes \iota\ 10)$, where every
 922 entry equals one. The binary operation is addition of unit cost, denoted `_+'_`, and the neutral
 923 element is zero.

924 $a : \text{Ar } (\iota\ 10 \otimes \iota\ 10 \otimes \iota\ 10)\ \mathbb{N}$ $_+'_ : (a\ b : \mathbb{N}) \rightarrow \mathbb{M}\ \mathbb{N}$
 925 $a = \text{K } 1$ $(a\ +' \ b)\ _ = 1, a + b$
 926

927 Helper functions `#s` and `#p` count the number of operations when scanning sequentially and
 928 in parallel, respectively:

929 $\#s : \text{Ar } s\ \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$ $\#p : \text{Ar } s\ \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{N}$
 930 $\#s\ a = \text{scan } _+'_ \ 0\ a\ \text{goSeq}.\text{proj}_1$ $\#p\ a = \text{scan } _+'_ \ 0\ a\ \text{goPar}.\text{proj}_1$
 931

932 We now compare the operation counts for right- and left-nested reshapes of a : reshapes of
 933 a :

934 $_ : \#s\ (\text{reshape } \triangleleft_r\ a) \equiv 3110$ $_ : \#s\ (\text{reshape } \triangleright_r\ a) \equiv 2210$
 935 $_ = \text{refl}$ $_ = \text{refl}$
 936

937 As can be seen, we have a significant difference in operation counts, as complexities of the
 938 corresponding algorithms are $O(n \log n)$ and $O(n)$. When running the same algorithms in
 939 parallel we obtain:

940 $_ : \#p\ (\text{reshape } \triangleleft_r\ a) \equiv 765$ $_ : \#p\ (\text{reshape } \triangleright_r\ a) \equiv 341$
 941 $_ = \text{refl}$ $_ = \text{refl}$
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943 Parallel execution reduces the runtime of both variants, but as both versions are highly
 944 concurrent, the left-nested version is still more efficient.

945 We have illustrated a single runtime model and two reshapes. Nevertheless, the effectful
 946 rank-polymorphic code defined above permits further performance engineering by identifying
 947 shape structures that best match the execution model of interest as well as adjusting hardware
 948 models. In general, a traversable monad may prove insufficient; additional monadic properties
 949 could be required. When runtime depends on the actual values stored in arrays, the proposed
 950 monadic approach may need to be extended. For simple cases one can define specialised
 951 `return/bind` operations for a particular datatype (cheating), whereas a more general solution
 952 would involve employing a richer effect system for such modelling.
 953

954 7 Related Work

955 The array theory presented herein draws inspiration from earlier work on containers [3]. We
 956 restrict the shapes of containers to products of natural numbers, and our reshapes correspond
 957 to Cartesian morphisms [1]. Containers prove extremely useful when modelling arrays. On
 958 the one hand, an explicit notion of shapes and indices affords a straightforward representation
 959 of arrays in concrete memory — we merely need to translate indices of a given shape into
 960 offsets. On the other hand, because arrays are modelled as functions, reasoning about array
 961 expressions becomes simpler; we can frequently exploit properties such as map-fusion through
 962 normalisation. Further developments of arrays as containers can be found in [36]. As this
 963 work deals with finite arrays, the theory of combinatorial species [35]—which are essentially
 964 finitary containers—is also relevant. Moreover, since our shapes possess a monoidal structure,
 965 the theory of operads [15] can be employed to interpret the proposed arrays.
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970 Due to limited space we presented only a single running example that demonstrates the
971 application of our technique. Nevertheless, a comparable treatment of arrays has proved
972 valuable in the following two scenarios. In [32] we consider an algorithm for blocked matrix
973 multiplication. Much as with scan, the tree structure of array shapes enables the encoding of a
974 blocking strategy for the input matrices. We define a high-level algorithm for blocked matrix
975 multiplication, prove its correctness, and use it as a guide to derive an implementation in the
976 array language SaC that performs on par with state-of-the-art libraries such as OpenBLAS and
977 MKL. In [31] we employ a similar array framework to define convolutional neural networks
978 using high-level array combinators. We provide an automatic-differentiation facility in Agda
979 together with a semantics-preserving optimiser and a code generator targeting Futhark for the
980 language of array combinators.
981

982 Many ideas that appear in [7] resonate with the spirit of this paper. Elliott defines a
983 language of (generic) functors comprising zero, one, and singleton, closed under sums,
984 products and composition. For a given algorithm such as scan, one then defines an instance of
985 the algorithm for every case of that functor language. Consequently, the chosen algorithm can
986 be computed for data structures expressible as generic functors. Containers are isomorphic [2]
987 to strictly positive functors, so all generic operations can be defined on containers as well.
988 The key differences in the present work are threefold: (i) The dependently-typed framework
989 permits reasoning about rank polymorphism — knowledge of array shapes may be deferred
990 until run-time — whereas the decomposition into generic functors advocated in [7] must
991 occur statically; (ii) Here we abstract over array representation — by selecting a model and
992 combinators the algorithm is guaranteed to compute on the chosen representation — whereas
993 computation via generic functors proceeds by translation, leaving optimisation to the compiler
994 and thereby introducing separate practical challenges; (iii) Most importantly, we furnish a
995 formal proof that isomorphic representations (as given by reshapes) yield identical results,
996 whereas with generic functors one must manually ensure, for example, that scans over Pair
997 $\times \text{Pair}$ and $\text{Pair} \circ \text{Pair}$ coincide. Finally, our use of monads provides precise numbers
998 that can be taken into account when adapting specifications to a particular hardware model.
999

1000 There exists a substantial body of array languages that support rank polymorphism to
1001 varying extents. Early untyped languages such as APL [12], J [28], and Nial [27] provide
1002 run-time rank polymorphism without any type or conformance guarantees. They offer a rich
1003 repertoire of rank-polymorphic array combinators and are valuable for rapid prototyping.
1004 Within this tradition, Trenchard More initiated the development of array theories [19]
1005 that focus on identifying universal equalities in the context of built-in rank-polymorphic
1006 combinators. This line of work culminated in Lenore Mullin’s Ψ -calculus [20], which is
1007 based on a universal abstraction of iteration spaces akin to the `imap` operator from Section 2.2.
1008

1009 Inspired by these ideas, many functional array languages strive to support rank poly-
1010 morphism: SaC [23], Qube [30], Accelerate [18], Jeremy Gibbons’ Naperian Functors [8],
1011 Remora [26], and ATL [14]. While languages such as SaC or Accelerate primarily target the
1012 generation of efficiently executable code, the others are chiefly concerned with providing
1013 static guarantees against out-of-bounds errors. A fully generic setting in which ranks may
1014 only be known at run-time necessitates dependent types, as embodied by the array theory
1015 presented in this paper or by the type system of Qube. When ranks are restricted to static
1016 (compile-time) values, many static guarantees can be obtained with a less expressive type
1017 system. For instance, [8] offers a Haskell framework — similar in spirit to our work —
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for handling statically-ranked multidimensional arrays. Remora [26] proposes a novel type system (without full dependent types) for statically-ranked arrays, furnishing numerous APL-specific features such as shape lifting. ATL [14] is a statically-ranked Coq-embedded language that provides safe static indexing. In principle, all of the aforementioned languages could implement a static variant of the scan specification presented here. SaC, for example, demonstrates [33] the expressive power of rank polymorphism. Nonetheless, reproducing our equivalence proof based on reshapes within those systems would likely be challenging.

Futhark [10] is a functional array language that prioritises parallel performance and type safety. In contrast to the languages discussed above, it does not support rank polymorphism at all, but it does provide a built-in scan primitive. Although convenient for users, this primitive often renders it difficult or impossible to control the run-time behaviour of a particular application.

In [11] the authors explore the compositional nature of the in-place algorithm introduced by Blelloch. It would be interesting to investigate whether a tidy translation exists between our specification and the one presented in that paper.

In [24] the authors demonstrate that specifications from a framework akin to the one presented here can be translated into high-performance languages. This technique, termed “extraction”, leverages the reflection capabilities of the underlying dependently-typed language. With a modest amount of effort, Agda specifications can be compiled into an array language of the user’s choice.

Our encoding of arrays bears a strong resemblance to the encoding of type theories using Categories with Families (CwFs) [6]. This is unsurprising, since arrays are essentially functions: `imap` behaves like λ , and `_[]` (selection) behaves like function application. Accordingly, the analogy proceeds as follows:

<code>Con</code> : Set	<code>Sh</code> : Set
<code>Sub</code> : Con \rightarrow Con \rightarrow Set	<code>Reshape</code> : Sh \rightarrow Sh \rightarrow Set
<code>Tm</code> : Con \rightarrow Ty \rightarrow Set	<code>Ar</code> : Sh \rightarrow Set \rightarrow Set

Array shapes play the role of contexts, and array indices correspond to variables. Reshapes act as substitutions that permit the remapping of variables/indices within an array expression. Arrays resemble terms, albeit with elements of arbitrary type; whereas terms are closed, their bodies are themselves terms. The crucial insight for both systems is that substitutions possess an inductive structure, allowing the action of a substitution (*i.e.* reshaping) to be defined inductively as well.

In a sense, the proposed array theory constitutes a rudimentary type theory, wherein the only types that variables may assume in a context (shape) are of the form `Fin` n for some natural number n . It would be intriguing to develop a closed array theory in which indices and arrays inhabit a single universe. In such a setting, array shapes would themselves be arrays, guaranteeing that any operation on shapes is immediately applicable to arrays. A minimal prerequisite for this construction would be the ability to embed the array theory presented in this paper into such a type theory. Our experiments, however, suggest that attaining this goal might require something akin to very dependent types [4].

8 Conclusions and Future Work

We dressed up rank polymorphism in dependent types, thereby obtaining a haute-couture collection of tools for constructing and formally reasoning about array-based algorithms. This collection comprises: an *array theory* that enables the definition of specifications without committing to any particular array implementation; the *initial model* of the array theory that supplies recursion over array shapes; *array combinators* defined as interfaces with fixed semantics, ensuring that efficient implementations can be instantiated for all models; and *inductive reshapes* that make it possible to prove our principal theorem concerning the stability of functions under reshapes.

We have demonstrated that our specification of `scan` can be transformed into algorithms exhibiting differing runtime characteristics merely by selecting a shape for the input array. The main theorem guarantees that applying `scan` to any reshaping of the input array that is admissible under `Reshape` yields identical values. We have shown how monads can be employed to model runtime properties such as sharing and parallelism of array expressions. Coupled with the freedom to choose a runtime representation of arrays and to define efficient combinators for that representation, this approach mitigates guesswork when selecting the optimal shape for a given hardware architecture. An additional benefit of the dependently-typed framework is that all computations are index-safe and all functions are provably terminating.

By no means we do claim that the given array framework is complete for expressing every conceivable numerical computation. Nevertheless, this work offers a perspective on handling collections that can be represented as containers possessing non-trivial shape structure.

The notion of arrays can be generalised by extending shapes with new constructors such as addition, exponentiation, or perhaps even dependent sums or products. Doing so would afford greater flexibility in grouping elements within arrays, albeit at the cost of increased complexity for rank-polymorphic functions and reshapes. The language of reshapes is not immutable—it may be extended (*e.g.* by admitting permutations) or restricted (*e.g.* by forbidding flattening) according to the problem at hand. The array combinators presented here remain universal provided that shapes include singleton and product constructors.

The notion of arrays can be generalised by extending shapes with new constructors such as addition, exponentiation, or perhaps even dependent sums or products. By doing so we obtain greater flexibility in grouping elements within arrays, although rank-polymorphic functions and reshapes become correspondingly more intricate. The language of reshapes is not immutable—it may be extended (*e.g.* by permitting permutations) or restricted (*e.g.* by forbidding flattening) according to the problem under consideration. The array combinators presented here remain universal provided that shapes include singleton and product constructors. Moreover, the theory can be readily expanded with additional array combinators without jeopardising the existing development.

The present contribution constitutes a first step toward a wealth of promising future work. Firstly, we aim to generate high-performance code from the proposed specifications. While it is unlikely that Agda alone can produce code competitive with highly optimised low-level libraries, it is straightforward to encapsulate the array definitions within a small DSL and perform code generation. Another substantial question concerns the translation of `scan`-like algorithms into in-place array updates as described in Blelloch’s original paper [5]. On a theoretical level, it would be interesting to investigate whether incorporating reshape equalities

into shape definitions simplifies specifications; however, this would necessitate moving to more expressive type theories that support quotient types.

9 Conflicts of Interest

None.

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